



This vector allows expression in *E. coli* of the MRP1 full length protein (13283 in the map), tagged with 6xHIS at the C-terminal end. All protocols regarding this expression system are available at: <https://www.oppf.rc-harwell.ac.uk/OPPF/protocols/>